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Parasitic and Elemental Contaminants in Top Soil from Selected Elementary School Playgrounds (ESPs): Children Exposure Risk (CER)

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ABSTRACT

Soil can harbor various biological and chemical contaminants, and the soil in elementary school playgrounds raises concerns due to children's geophagic behavior and tendencies toward pica. This investigation aims to examine the presence of parasitic organisms and elemental contaminants in soil samples from selected elementary school playgrounds. Ten composted topsoil samples were collected from playgrounds and analyzed for parasites and elemental content using standard methods. The results identified nine parasitic contaminants, including: *Entamoeba coli* (25.7%), *Chilomastix mesnili* (2.86%), *Ascaris lumbricoides* (48.6%), *Taenia* spp. (8.57%), *Trichinella spiralis* (2.86%), *Toxocara* spp. (2.86%), *Balantidium coli* (2.86%), *Strongyloides stercoralis* (2.86%), *Trichuris trichiura* (2.86%). The study also found the following elements present in the soil: arsenic (As = 0.32 – 0.84 mg/kg), cadmium (Cd = 7.78 – 20.5 mg/kg), chromium (Cr = 32.5 – 44.7 mg/kg), nickel (Ni = 18.6 – 76.6 mg/kg), and lead (Pb = 26.6 – 190 mg/kg). Notably, lead concentrations (190 mg/kg) in 10% of the samples exceeded

the Canadian Soil Guideline Value (CSGV) of 140 mg/kg. Contamination factors indicate that the soil is particularly contaminated with cadmium. In conclusion, the soil from the investigated elementary playgrounds is contaminated with parasites and cadmium, with lead levels in sample SP10 posing a significant risk to children with prolonged exposure.

Keywords: parasite, children, contaminates, element, playground, topsoil

1. INTRODUCTION

Children's frequent activities in school playgrounds, such as playing and hand-to-mouth behaviors, heighten their vulnerability to environmental contaminants present in topsoil. These contaminants include parasitic organisms and heavy metals, which can pose significant health risks. Parasitic infections, particularly soil-transmitted helminths (STHs) like *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Trichuris trichiura*, and hookworms, are prevalent in regions with inadequate sanitation. A study conducted in Edo State, Nigeria, revealed a substantial presence of STHs in primary school playgrounds, indicating a considerable risk of infection among schoolchildren (Ogbaini-Emovon *et al.*, 2019).

In addition to parasitic threats, elemental contamination in playground soils is a growing concern. Children's exposure to elements such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), and manganese (Mn) can occur through ingestion, inhalation, or dermal contact with contaminated soil and dust. Research in Lagos State, Nigeria, assessed the health risks associated with these metals in school environments. The study found that while manganese levels were within permissible limits, concentrations of lead, cadmium, and chromium exceeded recommended thresholds. The health risk assessment indicated potential carcinogenic risks to children, primarily through ingestion pathways (Durowoju *et al.*, 2018).

Similarly, a study in Ibadan North-West, Nigeria, examined heavy metal burdens in public primary school children related to playground soils and classroom dusts. The findings demonstrated that mean blood lead levels in urban areas were significantly higher than those in semi-rural areas, suggesting that playground soil contamination contributes to elevated blood lead levels in children (Adebamowo *et al.*, 2016). These studies underscore the critical need for comprehensive assessments of parasitic and elemental contaminants in school playgrounds. Such evaluations are essential to develop effective mitigation strategies and policies aimed at safeguarding children's health in educational settings.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study Area

The research was carried out in Abeokuta (7.1475° N, 3.3619° E) in Ogun State, Nigeria, during February 2024. Due to increasing urbanization and rapid population growth, the land area of Abeokuta, approximately 2320 km², has been expanding in all directions. The total population of the area is 593,140. The city is situated on a rocky ledge that overlooks the savanna and is encircled by forests. It is positioned in Nigeria's tropical rainforest zone, characterized by tall trees, a dense grass canopy, and two distinct seasons. Abeokuta experiences a mean monthly temperature ranging from 25.7 to 30.2 °C, relative humidity

exceeding 50%, and an annual rainfall of 2,000 mm. The soil from the elementary school playground chosen for the study were majorly sandy while few were clayey. A descriptive map of Abeokuta in Ogun State, Nigeria, can be found in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Map of Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria (Umoren et al., 2024a).

Table 1. Geographical Description of Sampled Elementary Schools.

Sample ID	Elementary School	Coordinates
SP01	St. Paul Public School, Oluwo	7.149906, 3.338015
SP02	Modern Nursery and primary School, Sodubi	7.178343, 3.394641
SP03	St. John Anglican School, Agejo	7.135427, 3.351266
SP04	Al-Soliat Nursery and Primary, School	7.184604, 3.283713
SP05	Christ Mark Academy, Fadaye	7.207945, 3.365740

SP06	St. John Primary School, Kuto	7.135428, 3.351274
SP07	African Church Grammar School, Ita Eko	7.141864, 3.328982
SP08	Praiseville Academy Ita, Eko	7.116185, 3.331482
SP09	St. John School III, Kuto	7.135428, 3.351270
SP10	Baptize Day Nursery and Primary School	7.144801, 3.369811

2. 2. Sample Collection and Processing

A total of ten composite soil samples was randomly collected from 0 - 10 cm of the top soil from 10 different elementary school playgrounds using a clean shovel. The samples collected were kept in transparent polythene bags and taken to the laboratory. The collection was done in the morning between the hours of 7:00 - 11:00 when the larvae and eggs of geohelminths are expected to be active and fresh. These soils were majorly sandy while few were clayey.

2. 3. Geo-helminthic Examination

The parasitic eggs and larvae were detected using modified Cobb's decanting and sieving method. One hundred (100) grams of the top soil samples was weight into a beaker containing 250 mL of 5% sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution, then stirred vigorously, then allowed to stand for some minute, the suspension was decanted into a large transparent plastic container.

The remaining sediment was stirred again with 5% sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution and the supernatant decanted. The process is repeated a third time, and then the sediment in the beaker is discarded. A properly stirred mixture of suspension (supernatant) was filtered through a sieve with pore size of 1000 μm into another plastic, leaving behind heavy particles on the top of the sieve. The sieve was shaken and submerged in the suspension to assist the nematodes pass through.

The residue was stained with lugols iodine solution while the filtrate was allowed to stand overnight for sedimentation. Afterward, the supernatant was decanted off and 15 ml of the sediment left was transferred into a centrifuge tube. The tube was centrifuged at 3000 rotations per minute (rpm) for five minutes to concentrate the parasitic ova, cysts, etc. After centrifugation, the supernatant was decanted carefully from the tube without shaking. Then the sediment was agitated gently by middle finger to redistributing the parasitic stages. Finally, the sediment was examined under an Olympus binocular microscope using x10 and x40 objectives.

2. 4. Digestion and Elemental Estimation

The digestion was carried according to a protocol described by Famuyiwa et al., (2022) and Umoren et al. (2024a; 2024b). All glassware used for the study was pre-treated with 5% trioxonitrate (IV) acid (HNO_3) and then cleaned with distilled water. *Aqua regia* was used to digest the prepared sample in a digestion flask, which was oven-dried at 35 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 15 minutes. One (1) g of the sample was transferred into the flask with 20 cm^3 of *aqua regia*. The mixture was cautiously stirred and then heated in a fume hood for several hours without time reference.

The samples were cooled, filtered and diluted with deionized water to mark (50 cm³) in a volumetric flask, then analyzed for element using an atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS).

2. 5. Contamination Factor (CF)

The degree of pollution can be estimated using various methods, the study however adopted the contamination factor for estimating the degree of elemental pollution in the soil. which was calculated using eqn. 1.

$$\text{Contamination Factor (CF)} = \frac{\text{Elemental Conc.}_{\text{sample}}}{\text{Elemental Conc.}_{\text{Crustal region}}} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

where: elemental Conc. *sample* is the concentration of element from the soil and Elemental Conc. *Crustal region* is the concentration of elements in the reference level. The level of contamination is classified as follows; CF<1 = Low, 1≤CF<3 = moderate, 3≤CF<6 = considerable, CF>6 = very high.

2. 6. Statistical analysis

Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 20, and *Chi*-square test were used to analyze data and test for significant differences where appropriate. Microsoft Excel 2016 was use for calculating the contamination factor and data visualization.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Parasitic Contamination

A total of nine (9) parasitic species was observed in this study, namely *A. lumbricoides*, *Entamoeba coli*, *Taenia* spp., *C. mensili*, *T. spiralis*, *Toxocara* spp., *B. coli*, *S. stercoralis* and *T. trichiura*. The parasites observed in the elementary school playground soil in Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria are as follows: *Entamoeba coli* was detected in St. Paul Public School, *Chilomastix mesnili* and *Ascaris lumbricoides* was detected in Modern Nursery and primary School, *Ascaris lumbricoides* and *Taenia* spp. was found in St. John Anglican School, *Trichinella spiralis* and *Taenia* spp. was detected in Al-Soliat Nursery and Primary School, *Entamoeba coli*, *Toxocara* spp. and *Ascaris lumbricoides* was observed in Christ Mark Academy, *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Entamoeba coli* and *Balantidium coli* was found in St. John Primary School, *Strongyloides stercoralis* and *Taenia* spp. was observed in African Church Grammar School, there was no parasitic observation in sample from Praiseville Academy. *Ascaris lumbricoides* and *Trichiuris trichiura* were observed in St. John School III while *Entamoeba coli* was observed in Baptize Day Nursery and Primary School.

The highest number of parasites was found in Christ Mark Academy (03), an equal number of parasites was found in Modern Nursery and primary School, Sodubi, St. John Anglican School, Agejo, Al-Soliat Nursery and Primary School, St. John Primary School, African Church Grammar School and St. John School III (02) while a single parasite was observed in St. Paul Public School and Baptize Day Nursery and Primary School (Figure 2).

The intensity of parasites in examined school playground soils is summarized in Table 2 and Figure 3. The highest parasite intensity recorded was for *Ascaris lumbricoides* at 28%,

followed by *Entamoeba coli* at 22% and *Taenia* spp. at 17%. The lowest parasitic intensity was observed for *Chilomastix mesnili* (6%), *Trichinella spiralis* (6%), *Toxocara* spp. (6%), *Balantidium coli* (5%), *Strongyloides stercoralis* (5%), and *Trichuris trichiura* (5%).

Figure 2. Number of parasites detected across SP soil.

More than a quarter of the global population is at risk of infections caused by soil-transmitted parasites, such as *Ascaris lumbricoides*, hookworm, *Trichuris trichiura*, and *Strongyloides stercoralis*. Infected individuals can present with a variety of medical and surgical conditions (Jourdan *et al.*, 2018). In this study, *A. lumbricoides* ranked as the most prevalent parasite species detected. Exposure to *A. lumbricoides* in pupils can lead to intestinal issues such as small bowel obstruction, volvulus, or intussusception. This may affect nutrition and intestinal microbiota, although *Ascaris* can also provide some protection against severe enteric infections (Cooper *et al.*, 2013; Strunz *et al.*, 2016).

Toxocara spp. is a helminth of animal origin and can potentially cause zoonotic infections, often associated with stray dogs and cats. However, the low prevalence of *Toxocara* spp. (1%) detected in this study is likely due to the fact that the majority (90%) of schools are fenced and gated. This finding aligns with a study from the Kathmandu Valley, Nepal (Shiba *et al.*, 2000), which reported a high prevalence of *A. lumbricoides* and a low prevalence of *Toxocara* spp.

Three intestinal protozoa were identified in the study: *Entamoeba coli*, *Clonorchis sinensis*, and *Balantidium coli*. However, the most frequently observed parasite, *Entamoeba coli*, (9%) is not pathogenic (Fernando *et al.*, 2021).

Table 2. Parasite Intensity in School Playground Soil.

Detected parasite	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent	Chi-Square Test	
<i>E. coli</i>	08	22.2	22.2	F	S
<i>C. mesnili</i>	02	5.6	27.8	58.8	0.21
<i>A. lumbricoides</i>	10	27.8	55.6		
<i>Taenia spp.</i>	06	16.7	72.2		
<i>T. spiralis</i>	02	5.6	77.8		
<i>Toxocara spp.</i>	02	5.6	83.3		
<i>B. coli</i>	02	5.6	88.9		
<i>S. stercoralis</i>	02	5.6	94.4		
<i>T. trichiura</i>	02	5.6	100		
Total	36	100			

NB: $p < 0.05$ is considered significant

Figure 3. Total Percentage Parasite intensity in school playground soils

Since these pathogenic parasites are primarily transmitted through poor hygiene practices, their prevalence could be significantly reduced or even eradicated by improving sanitation (Basualdo *et al.*, 2007).

According to Jourdan *et al.* (2018), *T. trichiura* is transmitted via a fecal–oral cycle, where embryonated eggs are ingested through food or contaminated hands, hatching into larvae that develop in the small intestine. Infection with *S. stercoralis* is associated with symptoms such as cough, dyspnea, wheezing, and hemoptysis, while chronic strongyloidiasis may present with asthenia, anorexia, nausea, abdominal pain, diarrhea, and abdominal tenderness. The low intensity of *T. trichiura*, *S. stercoralis*, and *T. spiralis* recorded in the study suggests minimal or no fecal contamination in the school playground soil.

3. 2. Elemental Concentration

The levels of elements present in the soil are presented in Table 3. Because there are no established soil guideline values (SGVs) for certain elements in Nigeria, comparisons were made with the commonly accepted SGVs from the UK Environmental Agency and the Canadian Soil Guideline Values (CSGV). The measured concentrations of the elements are: arsenic (As = 0.32 – 0.84 mg/kg), cadmium (Cd = 7.78–20.5 mg/kg), chromium (Cr = 32.5 – 44.7 mg/kg), nickel (Ni = 18.6 – 76.6 mg/kg), and lead (Pb = 26.6 – 190 mg/kg).

The chemical structures and oxidative states of various arsenic forms greatly influence their toxicity. Inorganic arsenic present in soil can be dangerous as it can be absorbed and transmitted through the food chain, impacting different living organisms (Shrivastava *et al.*, 2015). The maximum arsenic concentration was observed in sample SP08 (0.84 mg/kg), followed closely by SP02 (0.82 mg/kg). All arsenic levels in the samples remained within the SGVs established by the UK (40.0 mg/kg) and the CSGV (12.0 mg/kg).

According to the ATSDR's list, cadmium (Cd) is identified as the sixth most hazardous element (Negahdari *et al.*, 2021). Extended exposure to Cd can result in cellular mutagenesis, damage to the lungs, and injury to the testicles (Faridi *et al.*, 2015). The highest level of Cd was found in sample SP03 at 20.5 mg/kg, followed closely by SP08 at 17.1 mg/kg. Common sources of Cd include the combustion of petroleum fuels, plastics, glass, and pigments utilized in paints for playground equipment (Lawal *et al.*, 2015). The Cd concentrations in the samples were within the acceptable limits of the CSGV (22 mg/kg) and the UK standard (150 mg/kg).

Chromium(Cr) can be found in two forms: trivalent (Cr^{3+}) and hexavalent (Cr^{6+}), with Cr^{6+} being the more hazardous of the two. The highest concentration of Chromium was detected in sample SP02 at 44.7 mg/kg, followed closely by SP09 at 44.1 mg/kg. All chromium levels in the samples stayed within the SGVs set by the UK, which is 200 mg/kg.

Nickel (Ni) is a trace element that is essential for human health (Taiwo *et al.*, 2019). However, as pointed out by Umoren *et al.* (2024b), nickel possesses several toxicity mechanisms, such as sensitization and allergenic effects. Additionally, it is classified as a carcinogen and may cause teratogenic effects, chronic bronchitis, pulmonary embolism, cardiovascular issues, and cancers affecting the prostate, throat, and nose. The highest concentration of Ni was observed in sample SP10 at 76.6 mg/kg, followed by SP09 at 55.7 mg/kg. All Ni levels in the samples were below the UK standard of 200 mg/kg.

Lead (Pb) poisoning occurs due to exposure to Pb and can affect various parts of the human body, potentially resulting in issues related to the brain, intestines, and stomach (Umoren *et al.*, 2024b). The highest recorded Pb concentration was found in sample SP10 (190 mg/kg), followed by SP04 (86.6 mg/kg). The Pb level in one of the samples exceeded the CSGV (140

mg/kg) while remaining below the UK standard (450 mg/kg). The elementary playground SP10 is located near vehicle exhaust emissions, which may be associated with the elevated lead levels (Lawal *et al.*, 2015).

Table 3. Elemental concentration in soil.

Sample	As	Cd	Cr	Ni	Pb
SP01	0.58	14.2	32.5	21.3	28.6
SP02	0.82	15.7	44.7	27.3	37.6
SP03	0.32	20.5	32.8	38.6	42.1
SP04	0.76	12.8	33.2	18.6	86.6
SP05	0.35	9.57	36.1	29.7	46.9
SP06	0.70	15.2	32.9	25.5	26.6
SP07	0.44	12.9	35.6	33.3	35.3
SP08	0.84	17.1	34.8	47.9	51.8
SP09	0.35	7.78	44.1	55.7	60.4
SP10	0.46	11.7	41.6	76.6	190
Minimum	0.32	7.78	32.5	18.6	26.6
Mean	0.562	13.7	36.8	37.5	60.6
Maximum	0.84	20.5	44.7	76.6	190
Std. Dev.	0.20	3.68	4.79	17.9	48.7
UK (2013)	40	150	200	200	450
CSGV (2009)	12	22	-		140

3. 3. Contamination factor (CF)

The contamination factor of element in the soil is presented in Table 4, revealing that the soil has low contamination with As (0.0), Cr (0.51) and Ni (0.6), considerable with Pb (3.0) and very high with Cd (45.7). CF value in the descending order of Cd>Pb>Ni>Cr>As.

Table 4. Contamination factor for Element in top soil.

TEs	Mean	CF value	Grade	Degree of Contamination
As	0.562	0.0	CF<1	Low
Cd	13.7	45.7	CF>6	Very High
Cr	36.8	0.51	CF<1	Low
Ni	37.5	0.6	CF<1	Low
Pb	60.6	3.0	3≤CF<6	Considerable

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The research study investigated the presence of parasitic and elemental contaminants in the topsoil from ten selected elementary school playgrounds in Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. A total of nine parasitic species were detected: *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Entamoeba coli*, *Taenia* spp., *Strongyloides mensili*, *Trichinella spiralis*, *Toxocara* spp., *Balantidium coli*, *Strongyloides stercoralis*, and *Trichuris trichiura*. The findings revealed that the majority (9 out of 10) of the examined school playground soils were contaminated with at least one parasite.

The presence of these parasitic contaminants suggests that soil may play a significant role in the transmission of zoonotic parasitic diseases to children (pupils) who are exposed to it. As a result, the majority of the examined playgrounds pose a risk of developing parasitic diseases, including ascariasis, taeniasis, balantidiasis, toxocariasis, trichinosis, strongyloidiasis, and amoebic dysentery, particularly through the ingestion of soil.

Additionally, the study found elemental contaminants such as arsenic, cadmium, chromium, nickel, and lead in the soil. Notably, lead concentrations in one of the playgrounds exceeded the Canadian Soil Guideline Value (CSGV). The contamination factors indicated that the soil is particularly contaminated with cadmium. Overall, the soil from the investigated elementary school playgrounds is contaminated with both parasites and cadmium, while lead levels in sample SP10 present a significant risk to children with prolonged exposure. Based on these findings, it is recommended that pupils be educated about hygienic practices and ways to avoid soil ingestion.

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